

INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AS A FACTOR FOR IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN DEVELOPING SOCIAL RELATIONSHIPS IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the issues of improving the professional competence of innovative educational environment for the development of social relations in students. In addition, at the same time, it discusses the current innovative educational environment in Uzbekistan and the important aspect of the innovative educational environment for students.*

Keywords: *innovative education, student, professional competence, creative thinking, innovative processes, teacher, pedagogical process.*

INTRODUCTION

The current stage of the development of the society of independent Uzbekistan is characterized by a rapid change in technology, which leads to the formation of a new educational system that includes constant renewal. The success of continuous education depends on the ability of all subjects of the educational system to maintain competitiveness, and its most important conditions are personal characteristics such as activity, initiative, creative thinking and the ability to find non-standard solutions. Therefore, today in the republic One of the promising directions of education development is the improvement of professional skills, the dissemination of best practices and the creation of an innovative educational environment. shows, clearly knows his professional goals, is open to any news and optimistic about innovations. It is one of the most important tasks to educate such teachers and educators and prepare them for pedagogical activities. An innovative educational environment is the most important in the implementation of this important task.

METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

The problem of developing student's professional skills has been studied by many philosophers, pedagogues and psychologists. Many world scientists - V.A. Adolf, T.G. Brazhe, E.F. Zeera, I.A. Zimney, N.V. Kuzmina, M.I. Lukyanova, A.K. Markova, A.M. Novikov, G.S. Trofimova, G. Bernhard, V. Blum, H. Markus - have discussed the issues of formation and development of professional competence. , considered in the works of R. Sterner and others.

Professional competence is of particular importance, because the education system is currently characterized by significant innovative changes. In order to be successful and demanding in the current environment, a future educator or teacher should be ready for any changes, be able to quickly and effectively adapt to new conditions, show a desire to become a professional, constantly improve their knowledge and skills. it is permissible to renew and strive. For self-development, it is necessary to acquire the characteristics of tolerance for uncertainty, readiness for risks, that is, to be competent at the professional level.

However, social practice shows that these characteristics are not formed by all teachers. On the contrary, most of them experience great difficulties in adapting to rapidly changing social,

economic, and professional conditions, and then the lack of professional competence can cause serious social and psychological problems of the individual - from internal dissatisfaction to social confrontation and aggression. Therefore, the innovative educational environment is very important in developing the professional competence of future educators or teachers.

The success of the improvement and development of innovative education and the professional competence of students who are at the center of these educational processes and the development of social relations, in turn, in many ways, is the readiness of professional personnel working in the field of education to work in an innovative mode, flexible, their own it depends on the ability to quickly respond to the constantly changing needs of society and the individual in his professional activities. Therefore, the development of professional competence of students studying in higher educational institutions today is becoming one of the most important conditions for the reform of Uzbekistan's education.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this regard, it is important for the participants of the educational process to develop a psychological-pedagogical support program that helps students develop their professional competence in developing their social relations, contributes to the improvement of the quality of education and the formation of positive relationships among all students. is important.

At the moment, the education system of Uzbekistan is characterized by significant changes, as a result of which, first of all, it is possible to witness the activation of innovative processes.

Within the framework of the problem presented in the article, it is important to clarify the concept and structure of professional competence in connection with the conditions of the educational environment, in particular, its innovative nature.

Innovative activity in the field of education began to gain more and more importance throughout the world from the second half of the 20th century. This was related to the need to eliminate the crisis phenomena that clearly appeared in education during the transition to a post-industrial society, as well as the general trend that initially formed in the economy. Therefore, in order to understand the essence of innovation, innovative activity, innovative environment, it is important to take into account the economic understanding of this phenomenon.

The processes related to the first most complete description of innovative activity, innovative environment, innovation, etc. date back to 1911, and the name of the American economist I. Schumpeter should be mentioned first. Because these terms were introduced by the economist, and a little later, in the 1930s, I. Schumpeter and G. Mensch introduced the term "innovation" into scientific circulation.

CONCLUSION

In modern society, innovation is not only a condition for the existence of the economy, turning it into a socially oriented economy that works for people, but is also becoming the most important universal factor of controlled social development.

The main functions of innovative activity include changing the components of the pedagogical process, reflecting the content, goals, content, forms, methods, technologies, educational tools, management systems, etc. of education. At the same time, almost all researchers agree that not all types of research can be considered innovative, because innovations are purposeful, meaningful changes. Without ignoring these changes, it can be seen that the role of the

innovative educational environment in improving the professional competence of students in developing their social relations is incomparable.

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